

REVIEW OF PHYTOCHEMICAL AND NUTRITIONAL CHARACTERISTICS AND FOOD APPLICATIONS OF *CITRUS* L. FRUITS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112583>

Annotation: In this article discuss about review of phytochemical and nutritional characteristics and food applications of citrus L fruits and gives some important informations about them

Keywords: phytochemical, nutritional, food, citrus, characteristics, discuss

Since the dietary regimen rich in fruits is being widely recognized and encouraged, *Citrus* L. fruits have been growing in popularity worldwide due to their high amounts of health-promoting phytonutrients and bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids, phenolic acids, vitamins, carotenoids, pectins, and fatty acids. The diverse physicochemical properties and multiple utilization of citrus fruits in food industry are associated with their unique chemical compositions. Throughout the world, citrus has been used for producing various value-added and nutritionally enhanced products, including juices, wines, jams, canned citrus, and dried citrus. However, the current studies regarding the phytochemical and nutritional characteristics and food applications of citrus are scattered. This review systematically summarizes the existing bibliography on the chemical characteristics, functional and nutraceutical benefits, processing, and potential applications of citrus. A thorough understanding of this information may provide scientific guidance for better utilizing citrus as a functional fruit and benefit the extension of citrus value chain.

Citrus (genus *Citrus* L.), which belongs to the citrus genus of the *Rutaceae* family and *Aurantioideae* subfamily according to the botanical classification, is currently among the most economically important cultivated crops in terms of area and production values around the world. Citrus is believed to have originated in the Himalayan area of southwestern China, northeastern India, and northern Burma, and now has been diffused in more than 140 countries. According to statistics from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the total global production of citrus in 2019 was about 144 million tons, with a planting area of 9.89 million hectares, of which, the output and cultivation area of citrus in China reached 38 million tons and 2.88 million hectares, respectively, ranking first place worldwide. Sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*), sour orange (*C. aurantium*), mandarin (*C. reticulata*), grapefruit (*C. paradisi*), pummelo (*C. grandis*), lemon (*C. limon*), citron (*C. medica*), lime (*C. aurantifolia*), kumquat (*C. japonica*), and hybrids are known as the most commercially important citrus species.

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